

ANNUAL PLAN

20
24

MESSAGE FROM THE CHAIR

It has been an exceptionally exciting year within the ODISSEI community and the plans for 2024 contained within this report indicate that next year will be even more filled with new innovations, collaborations, and developments.

As we enter the 4th year of our Roadmap project, our community has reached new levels of maturity and activity that really bring the infrastructure to life. This year the ODISSEI Conference will welcome 450 participants and include almost 100 presentations from scholars across the social science domain. We have an active community of ODISSEI Summer School alumni, will be shortly announcing our first Social Data Science Team (SoDa) Fellow, and have awarded more than 30 grants in the last year. The scientific maturity of ODISSEI is particularly evident in the increasing impact in scientific publications, where we now see an ODISSEI publication appearing every 2-3 days and across a multitude of research areas. It is particularly great to see a new generation of scholars emerging that see the opportunities in ODISSEI anew.

The last year has also been an exciting one of renewal within the organisation of ODISSEI. We welcome several new Supervisory Board Members including Claes de Vreese (DSW), Viola Angelini (DEB), Beate Völker (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), Susan Branje (DSW), and Maarten van Ham (DSW). It is great to have an injection of drive and ambition within the project as we look forward to what we want to achieve over the next 10 years. In the Management Board there is also change as we welcome Daniel Oberski (UU) as a member of the Management Board and Chair-elect. Daniel has a broad knowledge of the field, grounded in methodological rigour and innovation. ODISSEI has achieved a lot in the seven years since its initial inception but this injection of new ideas coming from new members provides reassurance that we can build on an already solid foundation to really shift the empirical base of social and economic research in the Netherlands and open up new, fruitful lines of inquiry.

This process of renewal is already evident in many new national and international collaborations in which ODISSEI has started engaging. SSHOC-NL will launch in 2024 and is a major new investment in aligning infrastructures between the Social Sciences and Humanities. The potential of this new collaboration can already be seen in existing collaborations like the co-development of SANE, the secure research environment, and the linking of social history data in the Historical Sample of the Netherlands with the population registers at Statistics Netherlands. Internationally, ODISSEI also has an increasing influence and more intensive collaborations by supporting the development of major new European Research Infrastructures such as SoBigData Europe and the International Data Access Network. When engaging in these collaborations, it makes me exceptionally proud to hear talk of “following the ODISSEI model”. This means being open, transparent, collaborative, and innovative with broad support from the research community. I hope that model is evident in the programme of work for 2024 that we set out here.

PEARL DYKSTRA
CHAIR, ODISSEI

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GOVERNANCE

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GOVERNANCE

ODISSEI is the **Dutch National Infrastructure for Social Science** and provides access to a federated set of services to ODISSEI member organizations. Its explicit mission is to provide researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social enquiry.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as **innovative and diverse new forms of data**. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel, new ways

ODISSEI now consists of **45 member organisations** who have all signed the participants agreement and committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI until 2024, the end of the Roadmap project.

After 5 years of service, Pieter Hooimeijer, Carlo Schuengel, Henk van der Kolk, the three representatives of the Deans of Social Science on the ODISSEI Supervisor Board, ended their term as of 31st October 2023. As of 1 November 2023 the **Supervisory Board** consists of Viola Angelini (DEB), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Beate Völker (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), Susan Branje (DSW), Claes de Vreese (DSW), Maarten van Ham (DSW), and Paulette Flore (public research institutes). During the next meeting, the Supervisory Board will welcome new members and select the new chair.

The **Management Board** consists of eleven members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair), Tom Emery (EUR, Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Jessica Piotrowski (UvA), Daniel Oberski (UU), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ran van den Boom (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Collete Bos (NLeSC), Anja Smit (DANS), and Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work. Pearl Dykstra will continue as Chair of the ODISSEI Management Board until the end of 2024, and the ODISSEI Supervisory Board and Management Board has appointed Professor Daniel Oberski as Chair Elect of the Management Board. Dr. Tom Emery will take over Professor Dykstra's position as Director of ODISSEI as of November 2023.

The **Coordination Team** is composed of Tom Emery (Director), Lucas van der Meer (Chief Technical Officer), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Theodora Canciu (Project Manager), Evgeniia Krichever (Communications Manager), Angelica Maineri (Data Manager), Sofia den Haan (Project Management Officer) and Emilio Cammarata (Trainee).

An **International Advisory Board** has been established, including Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). Due to travel restrictions, the board has yet to meet in person, but a virtual meeting took place in May 2021, and a further meeting is planned for late 2023.

PROGRAMME OF WORK

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1

DATA FACILITY

1.1

CBS Microdata Access

1.2

ODISSEI Portal

1.3

ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

1.4

Secure Analysis Environment
(SANE)

The Data Facility aims at supporting access, linkage, and analysis of sensitive data in a safe, secure, and ethical manner.

1.1. CBS MICRODATA ACCESS

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands (CBS) and supports further development of the remote access environment.

Task leader

Ran van den Boom (r.vandenboom@cbs.nl)

ODISSEI continues to facilitate access to CBS microdata, targeting early-career researchers in particular. In early 2023, ODISSEI launched its annual call to facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands free of charge for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations (so-called Microdata Access Grants, MAG). Six projects were granted in Summer 2023. Despite modest grant amounts averaging €7,500, their impact is substantial, enabling projects otherwise infeasible. The Microdata Access Discount (MAD) administered in collaboration with Statistics Netherlands continues until the end 2023, backed by a €125,000 budget, effectively expanding microdata access, attracting more projects, and gradually reducing discount rates. A complete list of discounted projects is accessible on the [ODISSEI website](#).

In 2024 the MAD will be discontinued and CBS will allocate **€480,000** until the Roadmap project's conclusion to enhance remote access performance. Investments will focus on the self-service portal, facilitating user control in projects operating in the Remote Access Environment, strengthening automatic disclosure checks for standard output, and streamlining administrative processes in Microdata Services. Additionally, at least €75,000 of the total will fund additional Microdata Access Grants in 2024.

Research results: Diversity in the pathway from medical student to specialist in the Netherlands. Lianne Mulder et al., Amsterdam UMC

Microdata is exceptionally well suited to study various forms of social inequality. In this MAD project, the researchers studied the pathway toward becoming a specialised practitioner. Using the data from the national register of all physicians and specialists, the authors showed that the medical specialist population is not representative of the medical student population. The route to becoming a specialist is affected by early life experiences, impacting medical school enrollment and especially students with migration backgrounds were underrepresented among the those who successfully completed the specialisation.

Lianne Mulder et al. (2023). Diversity in the pathway from medical student to specialist in the Netherlands: a retrospective cohort study, *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe*. doi.org/10.1016/j.lanep.2023.100749

1.2. ODISSEI PORTAL

The ODISSEI Portal promotes the reuse of existing datasets by making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

Task leader

Jacco van Ossenbruggen (j.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

To facilitate FAIR use of data, the Portal provides a variable level, searchable catalogue of data within ODISSEI member organisations and beyond. Reusing and linking existing datasets can result in lower research costs, better data quality and richer data. Researchers can address new research questions by navigating the pre-existing data collections and rapidly identifying possible linkages and synergies between the data sources. The Portal working group consists of representatives from DANS, VU, SURF, and the ODISSEI Coordination Team. The Portal is live and being continuously developed with updates on a quarterly basis. In October 2023, the functionality of the Portal was further extended through metadata enrichments.

Currently, there are around 10 unique users per day, with an upscaling of usage planned for mid-2024 through a broad promotional push. The budget for this work in 2024 is **€771,235** and primarily consists of engineers, developers, and data stewards. In 2024, the Portal will be particularly extended to align with developments in the SSHOC-NL project and will include the work on linkage quality, efforts to build SSH FAIR & linked open data model, and development of the tools that will further support implementation of the FAIR principles in the SSH domains (including the detailed workflow for users to store their metadata according the FAIR principles and further integration between metadata Portals present in Social Sciences and Humanities domains).

1.3. ODISSEI SECURE SUPERCOMPUTER

The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer enables the analysis of highly sensitive administrative data in highly secure HPC environments.

Task leader

Michel Scheerman (michel.scheerman@surf.nl)

The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer and obeys the highest standards for data protection, both legally and technically. The OSSC was formally launched in October 2020 and transferred to Snellius, the national supercomputer, in 2022. Interest in the OSSC has been considerable and comes from a wide variety of member organisations, including organisations that are not ODISSEI members. Through 2024, at least a further seven projects will be supported in their implementation and usage of OSSC, with the Coordination Team monitoring progress. The OSSC team has finalised the sustainability plan and reports on demand for specific OSSC services to guide its usage in the future.

The operation of the OSSC in 2024 will cost **€341,550** and will be implemented by SURF and CBS. This covers necessary adaptations, an automatic reservation system, and user support to serve all member organisations. In the coming years, CBS aims to improve technical and legal support, making it easier to securely and ethically perform complex calculations on large datasets from different data providers and to extend the user base for the OSSC to cover both the Social Sciences and Humanities domains. The SSHOC-NL related developments will include upgraded authentication systems, pilot projects with complex genetic data, further integration within the ODISSEI Portal, and FAIRification of the study results through the FAIR result repository.

We are working on a structural econometrics model to study labour supply, savings, and pension claiming decision. The solution and estimation of the model are computationally demanding and it would be impossible to progress without the OSSC.

Mario Bernasconi, Tilburg University

1.4. SECURE ANALYSIS ENVIRONMENT (SANE)

The Secure analysis environment (SANE) is a virtual container that ensures the safety of the sensitive data and limits while enabling data analysis.

Task leader

Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

One issue that arises in social research is that data providers are reluctant to share sensitive datasets with researchers, as they cannot remain in control of the data during the analysis process, resulting in many relevant datasets being unavailable for the research community. The Secure ANalysis Environment (SANE) is a solution to this issue. SANE is a virtual, fully shielded computing environment containing pre-approved analysis software, such as R and Jupyter notebooks, and access to sensitive data. It allows the data provider to maintain complete control while allowing the researcher to study the data conveniently. The prototype was delivered in October 2023, and SANE demonstrated its security by passing a penetration test in September 2023. SANE is built on SURF Research Cloud, which is ISO 27001 certified. The facility is being extensively tested by eight pilot use cases from different data providers. Interest in using the facility is considerable among the data providers and researchers alike.

SANE is a PDI-SSH financed project which is executed as a collaboration between ODISSEI and CLARIAH, and is executed by SURF.

In the upcoming period, the team will move to the production environment and determine the legal framework for (international) data providers and researchers to use the facility. There is currently very high demand from data providers for use of SANE and this is expected to grow through 2024. Furthermore, the teams will integrate SANE into existing distributed generic infrastructure components and services already being used in the SSH ecosystem or national E-infrastructures such as SURF and DANS, to ensure that researchers can access easy-to-use sVREs (secure Virtual Research Environments) suitable for addressing a wide range of practical use cases. This will be done within the context of SSHOC-NL and the allocated budget for developments on SANE in 2024 are **€742,753**.

SANE is enabling us to take restricted data from the Dutch Chamber of Commerce (KvK) that has never been available at scale to researchers before and make it securely accessible via a flexible and powerful compute environment. It's an easy to use and simple solution to a common problem in social research.

Wolter Hassink, Co-PI Firmbackbone,
Utrecht University

2

OBSERVATORY

2.1

Data Collection Committee

2.2

LISS panel

2.3

Media Content Analysis Lab

The Observatory aims at sustaining and optimising valuable, long-standing data collections and collection and integration of new types of data.

2.1. DATA COLLECTION COMMITTEE

The Data Collection Committee finances critical large-scale data collections, ensures they have a sustainable future, and integrates them into a diverse data landscape.

Task leader

Marieke Knoef (M.G.Knoef@tilburguniversity.edu)

ODISSEI ensures Dutch participation in cross-national data collections, identifies gaps, and allocates resources for longitudinal data collections. The Committee has facilitated the transition of data collections to sustainable models. Four members have been appointed: Marieke Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, and Janine van der Maat. ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC) and surveys of key strategic importance. In 2024, ODISSEI is financing the position of CTO of SHARE (€50,000), and the collection of Wave 10 (€395,000) and the completion of the latest round of ESS (€172,561). ODISSEI will also pay the Dutch contribution for the Luxembourg Income Study (€30,000) and International Social Survey Programme (€40,000). ODISSEI will also work on retrieving information from archival person records held by the Central Bureau of Genealogy (CBG), which will fill the gap

between the current existing data systems HSNDB (1812-1920) and SSD (1994-today) and will form an infrastructure providing multi-generational life course and survey data. As Chair, Marieke Knoef also oversees a data scout, Marco Stam, who identifies new sources of data for integration within ODISSEI (the ODISSEI Portal, linkage to CBS Microdata, use of secure data environments such as SANE, etc), especially data that has not been collected for research purposes and particularly in the fields of Law and Economics which are currently under-represented within the ODISSEI framework. Marco works with potential data providers and existing ODISSEI services to facilitate access to such data sets, ensure their adequate documentation, and promote their usage. In 2024, this work will cost €26,238.

2.2. LISS PANEL

LISS is an online panel that provides researchers with the opportunity to field questionnaires, run experiments and collect high-quality research data in a cost-efficient way.

Task leader

Marcel Das (marcel.das@centerdata.nl)

The panel, which is run by Centerdata, consists of some 7,500 individuals from approximately 5,000 households and is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands. ODISSEI supports researchers through the open calls, which offer free panel time. The calls are exceptionally popular. Successful projects are showcased on the ODISSEI website and generate considerable press attention. The sixth round of the LISS panel grant closed in September 2023, and the award decision will be announced by mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2024. These calls cost **€95,000** for 2024 and cover two separate rounds of calls for the remaining period. ODISSEI will also provide a €375,000 subsidy to the LISS panel for its core operations and maintenance.

This budget will be used for the maintenance of the LISS panel in 2024. Centerdata provides a 20% discount for researchers fielding modules and experiments in the LISS panel to projects from ODISSEI member organisations. The LISS Panels position as a global leader in innovative data collection will be further strengthened by the integration of tools to execute simultaneous mass online experiments or data collection through data donation by the panel members. The pilots for those initiatives are already ongoing and will continue in the context of the SSHOC-NL project (**€160,000**). Oversampling of difficult to reach populations will ensure high data quality to study research questions that are otherwise difficult to answer.

LISS panel project: Perceptions of Inequality and Fiscal Policy Preferences. Oda Sund (University of Amsterdam)

This project focuses on citizens' perception of inequalities by documenting whether citizens hold accurate beliefs about wealth and income inequality (including their own relative position) and how they perceive the role of merit and luck in determining such inequality. Moreover, the project will causally identify the impact of these perceptions on citizens' acceptance of inequality and preferences for redistribution. Combining survey data with high-quality administrative data from CBS, the researchers will apply both experimental and quasi-experimental variations, providing highly relevant causal evidence for public policy.

2.3. MEDIA CONTENT ANALYSIS LAB

The ODISSEI Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) will offer opportunities for systematic analysis of large corpora of digital media content.

Task leader

Rens Vliegthart (rens.vliegthart@wur.nl)

MCAL tackles the major challenge of digital text analysis whereby copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data by providing a workbench for researchers where they can share data and analyses with strict rights management without the need to read or export the data themselves. Currently, several Dutch initiatives exist that facilitate retrieval, storage, and analysis of media content (i.e. the infrastructure for content analysis [INCA] at the University of Amsterdam (Trilling et al., 2018), and the Amsterdam Content Analysis Toolkit [AMCaT] at VU Amsterdam (Van Atteveldt et al., 2014). Their use, however, requires considerable programming skills and is currently tailored to a limited set of applications.

Thanks to a collaboration with the FAIR Expertise Hub and Triply, the transformation into Linked Data of an inventory of publications analysing media content in the Netherlands via TriplyDB provides an exemplary use case for the creation and governance of resources, e.g. controlled vocabularies and ontologies, to make data truly FAIR. Over the next year, this inventory will be used to develop a roadmap for the future intergration of large-scale media content data sources and existing analytical tools into the ODISSEI ecosystem and interoperable with services such as the ODISSEI portal and SANE.

The work will be conducted by post-docs appointed at WUR and UvA budgeted for **€88,498**.

3

LABORATORY

3.1

Port

3.2

Mass Online Experiments

3.3

Disclosure Risk in Networks

3.4

Benchmarking

The Laboratory aims to open up new avenues of scientific inquiry by exploiting innovative digital technologies.

3.1. DATA DONATION

Port is a software package that enables individuals to donate their digital trace data to academic research.

Task leader
Laura Boeschoten (L.boeschoten@uu.nl)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) grants all persons within the EU the right to an electronic copy of their personal data (e.g., WhatsApp messages or bank statements), in a so-called 'Data Download Package' (DDP). Citizens can, therefore, now consent to donate relevant information derived from their digital traces to trusted researchers, in a manner that is legally mandatory for data processing companies. The Port software (see Figure below), developed by Utrecht University, allows researchers to securely analyse DDP data. It achieves this by distributing the processing of individuals' data to the data subjects' own personal computers, where pseudo-anonymised summary statistics can be extracted and collated centrally with thousands of others. This preserves the privacy of research participants who retain control over their personal data.

Port will be made interoperable with other secure environments such as SANE and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer, requiring the implementation of the controlled vocabularies on data security and data access, and integration with SURF Research Drive, SURF Research Cloud and SURF Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure. It will be extended for use in exploratory analysis, in combination with vaults and extensive de-identification procedures. Finally, PORT will be integrated with LISS and other data collections so that participants in these studies can also donate their data.

This work will be led by Utrecht University and is financed by the SSHOC-NL grant. The total budget for this task in 2024 will be **€20,000** and will be scaled up over the course of the project.

Figure 1: Port Software: Step-by-step illustration of the workflow that allows for a privacy-preserving analysis of data download package

3.2. MASS ONLINE EXPERIMENTS

The Mass Experiment Online Lab facilitates experiments in which large numbers of participants simultaneously interact under controlled conditions.

Task leader

Rense Corten (r.corten@uu.nl)

Population-level experiments cannot be conducted in the traditional laboratory as they require scale in which network structure is systematically varied across multiple large-sized experimental populations. The Mass Experiment Online Lab overcomes the significant infrastructural and logistic challenges associated with the simultaneous networked participation of many participants and removes barriers-to-entry by providing methodological and organisational research facilities to interested but otherwise ill-equipped domain experts through a series of open calls. In 2020-2021, the Lab was piloted in an experiment on political polarisation with a further use case to extend the functionality in early 2022. The pilot experiments were built in the [Elixir](#) programming language, with over 2,000 participants each.

In parallel, the [OBELISS project](#), is developing software that facilitates the execution of behavioural experiments within the LISS panel and using the oTree platform. These two initiatives are stepping stones towards the maturation of a permanent suite of tools for deploying Mass Online Experiments and eliminating the fixed costs associated with such experiments for Dutch researchers. In the upcoming period, the team will evaluate different types of software that can be used and design a use case that will result in a list of requirements for the general experimental infrastructure to be developed. In 2024 there is a budget of **€122,156** reserved for this work.

Results: Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combatting misinformation: an experimental study. Jonas Stein et al., Utrecht University

Because fact-checking takes time, verdicts are usually reached after a message has gone viral. To study this phenomenon researchers designed an online mass experiment that enabled recipients of an online message to attach veracity assessments. In well-mixed communities, the public display of earlier veracity ratings indeed enhances the correct classification of true and false messages by subsequent users, but crowd intelligence backfires when false information is sequentially rated in ideologically segregated communities, suggesting that network segregation poses an important problem for community misinformation detection.

Stein, J., et al. (2023). Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combatting misinformation: an experimental study. Nature Scientific Reports. doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28597-x

3.3. DISCLOSURE RISK IN NETWORKS

Together with POPNET, ODISSEI supports analysis of longitudinal network data on the entire population of the Netherlands and helps understand the disclosure risks inherent in such research.

Task leader

Frank Takes (takes@liacs.nl)

With an increased reliance on non-research data for scientific research, it becomes increasingly difficult to balance data access and data protection, both from a legal and ethical perspective. The most advanced current use case of data disclosure risk assessment is the analysis of network data extracted from CBS administrative records. This is because the data is highly sensitive, but also exceptionally complex and intensively linked, making disclosure risks particularly hard to assess with conventional approaches common in the areas of statistical disclosure control. Nevertheless, POPNET, ODISSEI's partner, has broken new ground in devising disclosure risk assessment methods that ensure a low risk of data disclosure whilst preserving the high scientific value of the data. An initial version of the POPNET tool has been developed to assess the disclosure risks within a specific dataset rapidly and at scale.

POPNET collaborates intensively with CBS to assess the data disclosure risk at multiple points in the data lifecycle and ensures that these risks are managed and minimised, whilst still providing scientists with the ability to analyse the data through a flexible and user-friendly interface. In SSHOC-NL, the POPNET tool will be made interoperable with a wider range of Social Science and Humanities data, including social media network data and development of methods to increase the interoperability of historical records. The work will be executed by Eelke Heemskerk (University of Amsterdam) and Frank Takes (Leiden University) and is financed by the SSHOC-NL grant. The total budget for this task in 2024 will be **€207,512**.

3.4. BENCHMARKING

ODISSEI's benchmark platform allows a large number of researchers to come together and collaborate on some of the most pressing and difficult questions in social research.

Task leader

Paulina Pankowska (p.k.pankowska@uu.nl)

Benchmarking is about creating a system of reference, in which various models that address the same task can be compared in order to be able to analyse the strength and weaknesses of various approaches and gain new insights. Using the ODISSEI infrastructure, the benchmarking challenge was embedded within the ODISSEI Summer School to utilise linked administrative data. In 2022 this task deployed benchmarking challenges using ODISSEI infrastructure, which was the first social science benchmark to utilise linked administrative data. In collaboration with Dr. Gert Stulp from University of Groningen, the participants of the 2023 iteration of the summer school were asked to predict the fertility using LISS panel data and administrative data (see the case study for the results of the summer benchmarking challenge).

This effort will be continued in 2024, when the team will run an open challenge based on the same principles and data and which will be open for the broad scientific community to join. In 2024, the cost of coordinating the benchmarking project will be **€70,000** for the year and run until the end of the roadmap project with a challenge embedded in each subsequent ODISSEI Summer School. The work is led by Paulina Pankowska in collaboration with the coordination team and SoDa. As part of this, ODISSEI is investing in benchmarking infrastructure: software that will be the starter kit 'Software-as-a-service' infrastructure for benchmarking, which will facilitate support, standardise and ease the design and implementation of benchmarks for the social sciences. The work will be executed in collaboration with the software company Eyra.

Use case: ODISSEI- SICSS Benchmarking challenge

During the challenge, the teams used two datasets (first LISS panel data then CBS microdata) to predict having a(nother) child within the next three years (2020-2022) based on data up to and including 2019. Participants were able to predict the outcome moderately well (although they only worked on the task for two weeks) even for the LISS test set, in spite of its relatively small sample size. The [leaderboard](#) for this challenge was created in the benchmarking infrastructure built by Eyra.

4

HUB

4.1

Coordination

4.2

Education

4.3

Support

The Hub aims to create a community of infrastructure users and offer the researchers the necessary support to enable complex and comprehensive modelling of social phenomena.

4.1. COORDINATION

The Coordination Team that is based at EUR is responsible for communicating the full potential of ODISSEI facilities to the research community and engaging ODISSEI partners.

Task leader

Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

ODISSEI has 45 member organisations but is continuously attracting new members. The ODISSEI Coordination Team at EUR works across those member organisations to reach potential users and engage them in using the research infrastructure. Some potential users are often unaware of the infrastructure's full potential, especially regarding new innovations and techniques made possible by linked services. Through community management, the team ensures that all potential users in relevant disciplines are made aware of ODISSEI's potential so they can understand what kinds of research are supported (**inform**: newsletter, website, podcast series posts on LinkedIn and X - previous Twitter). Researchers are then encouraged to take the next step in actively using the infrastructure and utilising specific services (**involve**: annual conference, task insights meetings, active Slack community, lunch lecture series).

Those who are already using the services are then also stimulated to stay involved and deepen their involvement through active community participation (**engage**: grant information workshops, ODISSEI introduction presentations, partner event).

Community Management also handles secretarial responsibilities to support the Supervisory Board, Management Board, and task leaders in their duties. The community management costs for 2024 include the costs of the 4.5 FTE in the ODISSEI coordination team (**€438,370**), all events including the ODISSEI Community Conference (**€50,000**), Community Management of ASReview (**€45,000**) and material costs for travel, events, and training across the project (**€148,000**). The ODISSEI Coordination Team also leads the implementation of the SSHOC-NL Project

4.2. EDUCATION

ODISSEI provides an educational programme including workshops, resources, and an intensive summer school to enhance training and skills acquisition in the Dutch Computational Social Sciences domain.

Task leader

Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

In 2023, ODISSEI organised its second ODISSEI Summer School in Computational Social Science in collaboration with SICSS. This summer school provided 21 participants with two full weeks of intensive training necessary to use complex elements of the ODISSEI infrastructure. It included modules on network analysis, machine learning, benchmark approaches, and the ethics of big data. The workshops were delivered by the Social Data Science (SoDa) team, the Benchmarking team, the eScience Center, and Coordination Team. The summer school is accredited with ECTS points for graduate students. In 2024, a repeat and potential expansion of the summer school is planned. The summer school complements a broader programme of workshops that is geared towards using specific ODISSEI facilities, such as the Microdata Access Grant, the LISS panel Grant and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer.

These workshops aim to showcase ODISSEI facilities and lower the threshold for submitting a project proposal. The programme is developed in collaboration with and executed by, or together with, several ODISSEI partners: DANS, CBS, Centerdata, Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC), and SURF. In 2024, the educational team plans to conduct about 5 workshops covering ODISSEI infrastructure use and thematic areas like geospatial or network analysis as well as workshops in collaboration with CLARIAH as part of SSHOC-NL. The task in 2024 will cost around **€143,721**. This includes coordination and event hosting expenses, such as the ODISSEI Summer School and the preparation of training materials.

The ODISSEI Summer School was one of the most useful workshops I ever participated in. In two weeks, I worked with wonderful and inspiring people, learned how to work with Python, mastered the machine learning methods and benchmarking principles, was able to work with extremely rich data of Statistic Netherlands, and got acquainted with other bits of the ODISSEI infrastructure. This was a truly inspiring experience, and I recommend others to join the programme next year.

Vardan Barsegyan, WODC

4.3. SUPPORT

ODISSEI bridges the gap between social scientists and infrastructure by providing active support in the use of the data and analytical infrastructure.

Task leader

Daniel Oberski (d.Loberski@uu.nl)

In ODISSEI, research support is delivered directly through access to technical and methodological expertise within the Social Data Science (SoDa) team, Research Software Engineers (RSE) of the eScience Center and FAIR Expertise Hub for the Social Sciences. Each team offers different types of support.

The SoDa team engages in short-term collaborative projects with social scientists across ODISSEI member organisations, to address innovative research questions and provide support with other infrastructure components, including OSSC, Microdata, eScience, and LISS panel. The team also offers a fellowship program starting from September 2023. The program seeks to provide early career researchers with paid opportunities to develop skills under the supervision of team members and spread this expertise in the ODISSEI community.

The eScience Center team supports projects that align with the ODISSEI strategic goals, with a strong emphasis on projects using the administrative data to be executed in the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC). At the same time, the FAIR Expertise Hub assists researchers and data providers in applying the FAIR principles and documenting their efforts via FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).

SoDa team executes 7 projects per year, on average with room for new projects during 2024. In the period 2024, NLeSC will provide further and more intensive support to several projects, with the first project to benefit being a synthetic data project by the University of Maastricht that is being executed in the OSSC. The support activities by the FAIR Expertise Hub (a PDI-SSH financed project) will continue until the end of 2024. The budget for all support tasks in 2024 will be **€859,530**.

SoDa team helped us develop the ArtScraper, a python library for scraping artworks from the Google Arts and Culture website, which created a large artwork collection for our project. The team also supported us when we started using the package by offering troubleshooting, fine-tuning, and improving it. The SoDa team's support was key to the efficient execution of this project, which would have been challenging to execute on this scale otherwise.

Eftychia Stamkou, UvA

FINANCIAL OVERVIEW

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FINANCIAL REPORTING

2022-2023

Up until now, ODISSEI has operated with a financial year running from July 1st to June 30th. As of this Annual Plan, this financial year will change to run from January 1st to December 31st. Therefore, with regards to financial reporting this Annual Plan serves two functions. The first is to provide the final financial reporting according to the old financial year and specifically the final reports for the year 2022-23. Secondly, in section 4, the Financial plan will be provided for the year 2024. This follows the initial approval of the financial plan for the period 2023-24 in June 2023 by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board. From 2024, ODISSEI will then operate using the new financial year with an Annual plan for the forthcoming year presented in the fall, and a financial report of the previous year presented in the spring. The first financial report under this new calendar will be in spring 2025.

Table 1 below shows the financial results for 2023-24. The financial reports for the period 2016-2023 include only NWO Infrastructure Development Grants, including the ODISSEI Roadmap project and the contributions of members. This reporting does not include additional projects such as 'Platform for Digital Infrastructure' (PDI-SSH) projects or SoBigData. In section 4 and for all future financial reporting, ODISSEI will include all projects in which EUR participates as providers of ODISSEI including SSHOC-NL, PDI-SSH and any national or European Grants in which ODISSEI is explicitly referenced in project agreements. This shift reflects the expanding portfolio of projects which ODISSEI is engaged in and the continuity evident in these projects.

The revenue for 2022-23 reflects the cessation of NWO contributions to ODISSEI's core operations which had initially been provided prior to the receipt of the ODISSEI Roadmap grant in order to support ODISSEI's development. When this contribution was first awarded, the member organisation contributions were just €125,000 per year but have since grown to €753,000 per year to reflect the support for the infrastructure amongst the wider research community. ODISSEI has largely saturated potential member organisations with 45 organisations now contributing annually.

The expenses for operating ODISSEI for the last financial year were €3.1 million with a net spend of -€0.2 million resulting in a cash reserve of €2.9 million. This cash reserve will be combined with the final €2 million instalment for the roadmap project to finance ODISSEI until the end of the Roadmap project at the end of 2024. As per the Annual Plan for 2023-24 that was approved in June 2023, expenditures up until the end of 2024 for the Roadmap project are expected to be €4.1 million so this current cash reserve largely reflects the frontloading of financing within the Roadmap project.

Table 1 – Financial reporting for 2022-23 with 2016-2022 for reference

	16-17	17-18	18-19	19-20	20-21	21-22	22-23
Income	525	1,040	1,587	1,175	3,749	4,103	2,889
NWO contribution	400	550	550	550	550	550	
NWO Bridge grant			487				
NWO Roadmap grant					2,524	2,685	2,136
Member organisations	125	490	550	625	675	725	753
Fieldwork contributions						143	
Expenses	287	852	1,372	1,393	1,903	3,297	3,111
Data Facility		35	603	464	753	1,279	1,000
1.1 Microdata		35	278	296	330	343	430
1.2 Use cases					0	25	
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer			325	85	216	692	345
1.4 Portal				83	207	219	225
Observatory	280	799	30	81	365	582	854
2.1 Data collection	280	799	30	81	334	279	718
2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab					10	60	59
2.3 Historical Sample of NL					21	180	
2.4 Netherlands Twin Register					0	63	78
Laboratory	0		640	660	319	761	365
3.1 Distributed Analytics					74	82	91
3.2 Automatic Metadata					34	89	92
3.3 LISS	0		640	660	203	460	182
3.4 Mass Experiments					9	53	
3.5 Citizen Science					0	77	
Hub	7	18	99	188	466	674	892
4.1 Community Management	7	18	99	188	304	362	440
4.2 Education				0	0	34	29
4.3 SoDa					161	118	150
4.4 Pathfinder grants					2	145	212
4.5 Benchmarks					0	16	60
Result (income minus expenses)	238	188	215	-218	1,846	806	-222
Cash reserve (accumulated result)	238	426	641	423	2,269	3,075	2,853

FINANCIAL PLAN 2024

Table 2 below represents the planned expenditures for 2024 and includes multiple projects in which ODISSEI will be engaged through this period. Because ODISSEI is an infrastructure and not a collection of unrelated projects, core *tasks* have been identified which are identifiable within ODISSEI. These are the tasks that structure section 2 of the annual plan and the table below illustrates the planned expenditure for these activities in 2024 and from which project they will be financed. The ODISSEI Coordination Team works closely with service providers to ensure continuity and coordination between projects to avoid duplication and realise efficiencies in implementation. During 2024 ODISSEI will be operating two concurrent Large Scale Infrastructure Projects and therefore the planned expenditures are higher than in previous years.

The tasks in each project are closely monitored on an annual basis by the ODISSEI Management Board and their budgets are then adjusted to optimise the tasks' development and deliverables for the ODISSEI community. The task marked 'CLARIAH' represents activities within SSHOC-NL which are dominated by CLARIAH and whose ODISSEI involvement is limited. The majority of tasks in SSHOC-NL are collaborative but a small number concentrate on key investments in the respective ODISSEI and CLARIAH communities. In SSHOC-NL, tasks 2.3 and 3.1 represent these CLARIAH specific tasks.

Table 2 – Budget Plan for 2024

ODISSEI Tasks	Stream	Roadmap Tasks	SSHOC-NL Tasks	Other Projects	Roadmap	SSHOC-NL	Other	Total
CBS	Data Facility	1.1			480			480
Portal	Data Facility	1.4; 3.1	4.1; 4.2; 4.3		319	452		771
OSSC	Data Facility	1.3; 2.4	1.3		248	94		342
SANE	Data Facility		1.1	SANE		115	628	743
Data Collection	Observatory	2.1; 2.3	2.2		237	479		715
LISS panel	Observatory	3.3	2.1		460	160		620
MCAL	Observatory	2.2			88			88
PORT	Laboratory		1.2			20		20
Mass Online Experiments	Laboratory		3.3			122		122
Disclosure Risk in Networks	Laboratory		3.2			208		208
Benchmark	Laboratory	4.5			70			70
Coordination	Hub	4.1	5.3		596	105	35	736
Education	Hub	4.2	5.2		40	104		144
Support	Hub	4.3; 4.4	5.1	FIP	352	306	200	859
CLARIAH			2.3; 3.1			267		267
Total					2,092	1,979	863	4,933

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KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

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KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were initiated at the beginning of the current Roadmap period. Each year, the current status of each KPI is reported and new targets are established. The KPIs are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board and amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board to ensure continuity and alignment with regard to the specific and concrete aims of the project.

Table 3 – Key Performance Indicators

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Target</i>	<i>Current</i>
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and 9 economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025	All social science faculties and 9 Economics faculties are members.
Participation in European projects	Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025	ODISSEI is now a partner in SoBigData Europe and investigating further projects.
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE by 2024	Initial contact has been made with discussion of formalisation
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	Currently approximately 7% of all researchers have submitted
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025	Currently 1% of all researchers have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	50 unique visitors per month by 2025	10 unique visitors per month
Number of OSSC Projects per year	7 per year for 2022, 2023 and 2024	15 in 2023
Number of projects spanning more than 2 service providers	5 per year by 2025	6 projects in 2023
Financial		
Further successful funding applications	Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH	2022 Roadmap proposal and SSO proposal submitted, Roadmap granted
Total amount committed by member organisations	By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum	Current contributions are perpetual but no commitments until 2029
Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	600 unique attendees at events per year	630 for 2023

Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	15 projects completed before end of 2024	20 projects acquired up to October 2023
Science & Technology		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	3 per year by 2025	3 up to 2023
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	30 per year by 2025	31 in 2022-2023 (until October)
Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	200 per year by 2025	106 in 2022-2023
Social and Economic Impact		
Number of datasets contributed by non-academic organisations	Five datasets from non-academic organisations accessible by 2025	8
Number of government agencies participating as member organisations	7 by 2025	6
Number of website visits	50,000 per year by 2025	44,447 in 2022-2023
Mentions in key policy documents	3 per year	Monitoring as of 2023
Press mentions of ODISSEI related research in the Netherlands	10 per year	Monitoring as of 2023
Communication		
Number of social media (e.g. X(Twitter), LinkedIn) subscribers	2,500 by 2025	1618 (50% growth per year, projected at 2,202 by 2025)
Number of newsletter subscribers	Total of 1,000 by 2025	1293 up to October 2023
Attracting New Talent		
Number of international scientists recruited by ODISSEI	20 by the end of 2024	Reported in 2024
Number of major grants using ODISSEI (e.g. NWO talent, MCSA, ERC etc)	5 per year	7 in 2023

RISK REGISTER

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RISK REGISTER

The ODISSEI Risk Register is designed to support the strategic planning and decision making of the Coordination Team, the Management Board, and the Supervisory Board. Risk assessments are always subjective, but consolidating the risk assessments into a singular document can help identify common risks, differences in risk perceptions across the project and interdependent mitigation strategies. The full risk register appears at the end of this document and has been used to create an overview of the various challenges faced by ODISSEI.

The high probability, high impact risks for this year were identified by Task Leaders, the Coordination Team and the Management Board and listed in Table 4. All the risks have been explicitly discussed by the Management Board and are being actively monitored by Task Leaders and Coordination Team contacts. As the ODISSEI Roadmap project enters its last phase, the probability of many risks occurring reduces. A core risk is in the OSSC, where the signing of several updated legal documents is substantially delayed. This resulted in having to postpone several OSSC projects. This issue was escalated at both CBS and SURF, now ensuring the involvement and availability of the organisations' highest legal councils. It is expected that the issue will be resolved in the coming months.

A second core risk is the alignment between the OSSC, Portal, SANE, and the wider ODISSEI ecosystem. Entering the last project phase, the increased need for alignment of the user processes has become clear. In addition, the importance and size of the OSSC justifies an end-of-project reevaluation of its user needs. To mitigate these risks, a SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy and an OSSC User evaluation will be developed by a joint working group between SURF and the ODISSEI Coordination Team. To oversee these developments, a new technical project manager overseeing all ODISSEI projects will be appointed at SURF, complementing the SURF-ODISSEI Research Partnership Lead.

Finally, a more intensive alignment between the LISS panel and the Portal team was needed, compared to what we expected at the beginning of the project. To tackle this issue, extra funds were freed to facilitate the integration and a joint working group will meet periodically to oversee these developments.

Table 4 - High Probability, High Impact Risks

<i>Task</i>	<i>Mitigation</i>
1.3 Delay in the signing of legal documents	Escalated to higher level; periodic project group meetings
1.3 Misalignment with wider ODISSEI ecosystem	A SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy and OSSC User evaluation will be developed.
2.2 Insufficient alignment with the Portal team	Joint working group; funds made available

Table 5 - Full Risk Register

<i>Task</i>	<i>#</i>	<i>Risk</i>	<i>Prob¹</i>	<i>Imp²</i>	<i>Mitigating Action</i>	<i>Risk Area</i>
Data Facility						
1.1	1	Restrictions in the usage of CBS microdata, e.g., as a follow-up of the external investigation into the security of Microdata Services	1	3	Increase technical and procedural safety warrants so that the research process itself is not affected more than necessary	Legal
1.1	2	Increased usage to an extent that the MAD percentage to an undesirably low level, that might cause some members to consider leaving ODISSEI	2	2	After a careful consideration with users, the MAD will be terminated this year.	High Demand
1.1	3	Unequal usage of the MAD across scientific domains and categories of users	2	3	After a careful consideration with users, the MAD will be terminated this year.	Low Demand
1.1	4	The self-service portal is not feasible within time and budget	1	2	Propose smaller scale, stepwise innovations in agreement with the user council	Sustainability
1.2	1	Not being able to hire and retain appropriate staff	1	3	Widely setting out vacancies, possibility to outsource the hiring.	Staffing
1.2	2	Misalignment (strategic or technical) between the partners	2	3	Bi-weekly, low-profile steering group and technical meetings	Coordination
1.2	3	Potential metadata providers not willing to or able to (automatically) share metadata, or to invest in altering metadata	2	3	Representatives in the ODISSEI Management Board. Cooperating with the ODISSEI Fieldwork Committee. Support and money available.	FAIR
1.2	4	Insufficient need for the Portal	1	3	Three-monthly user tests, presenting early versions at conferences, creating use cases, close collaboration with the social science research community.	Low Demand
1.2	5	Challenge to integrate the different components into one system	2	2	Coordination between partners and commonly designing technical infrastructure	Coordination
1.2	6	Lack of commitment for sustaining infrastructure after period 4	1	3	DANS committed to sustain the built infrastructure for at least five years.	Sustainability
1.2	7	Insufficient knowledge and consensus on explicit semantics of social-science metadata to develop a search interface with sufficient added value for social science researchers	2	3	Make use of existing standardisation efforts in the community, including the CESSDA metadata models and thesauri.	FAIR
1.3	1	Misalignment between SURF and CBS	2	3	The team will have periodic meetings	Coordination
1.3	2	Misalignment with wider ODISSEI ecosystem	3	3	A SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy will be developed.	Coordination
1.3	3	Too difficult OSSC user interface	2	2	Working on a graphic interface, education (Education task)	Technical
1.3	4	Delay in the signing of legal documents	3	3	Escalated to higher level; periodic project group meetings	Legal

¹ Probability: 3 = high, 2 = medium, 1 = low

² Impact

<i>Task</i>	<i>#</i>	<i>Risk</i>	<i>Prob¹</i>	<i>Imp²</i>	<i>Mitigating Action</i>	<i>Risk Area</i>
Observatory						
2.1	1	High non-response in online data collections	3	2	Knowledge exchange and shared results of online data collection	Technical
2.1	2	Low cooperation between data scouts and wider ODISSEI ecosystem (e.g. Portal and SANE)	2	2	Data Scouts need to be well embedded within the ODISSEI community and aware of the value added by ODISSEI	Coordination
2.1	3	No further funding for data collections	2	3	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications	Sustainability
2.2	1	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is limited	1	3	Invest more efforts in advertising the Calls, and promotion of the possibilities the Calls offers	Low Demand
2.2	2	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is overwhelming, leading to very low award rate	2	2	Make calls more thematically focused; merge funds for two calls; limit the target population to e.g. early career researchers only	High Demand
2.2	3	Attrition LISS panel is non-random making the panel less representative of the Dutch (speaking) population	2	3	Intensify panel care; correct for biases with stratified refreshment samples; increase efforts to minimise attrition; if needed reallocate budget to fund additional refreshment samples	Technical
2.2	4	Response rates decrease in monthly questionnaires and experiments fielded in the LISS panel	2	2	Motivate respondents to participate using response-enhancing measures, e.g. attractiveness of questionnaires and experiments, higher monetary incentives	Technical
2.2	5	Many panel members stop participating due to personal data breaches	1	3	Continuously monitor data security. Act proactively in case of a personal data breach or data leak	Legal
2.2	6	Increasing number of respondents opt-out when asked permission to link LISS data to register data, making linking less attractive for scientific research	2	2	Better explain what linking entails and that no identifying information will be made public	Technical
2.2	7	Delay in dissemination data via the LISS Data Archive due to restricted personnel capacity	1	2	Increase capacity; prioritise dissemination (first disseminate modules core study, then ODISSEI LISS Call projects, followed by other projects)	FAIR
2.2	8	Funding via the Domeinplan-SSH stops	1	3	Intensify efforts to acquire external funding	Sustainability
2.2	9	Insufficient alignment with the Portal team	3	3	Joint working group; funds made available	Coordination
2.3	1	MCAL not embedded in wider ODISSEI community	2	3	Ensure regular contact between MCAL team and wider ODISSEI Tasks	Coordination
2.3	2	Shifting investment and user requirements	3	2	The content analysis landscape is very dynamic, and an agile approach is therefore being adopted for its development	Low Demand
Laboratory						
3.1	1	Scarcity of IT personnel and development companies	2	3	Continuing work with partners with whom we have positive experience	Staffing

Task	#	Risk	Prob ¹	Imp ²	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
					and form a group of all researchers who can learn from each other's work and form a safety net in case someone (temporarily) leaves.	
3.1	2	Existing solutions cannot be integrated or do not meet the identified use-cases.			Careful match of multiple use-cases with various existing tools. Consultation with a broad audience of Port users before making decisions..	Technical
3.2	1	Limited reusability of building blocks	2	3	Start with relatively simple experiments using common design features; introduce more specific features later.	Technical
3.2	2	Limited sustainability of support	3	3	Develop open-source with careful documentation to keep developed code accessible. Host support at a robust and committed organisation.	Sustainability
3.2	3	Lack of uptake by broader research community	1	3	Promote the project widely, using the project website, conferences, and newsletters	Low Demand
3.3	1	Difficulty in attracting sufficient talent due to tight job market	1	2	Dissemination of job ads of the first open positions through as many relevant channels as possible, making use of both scientific and research infrastructure "networks of" contacts of the task leaders.	Staffing
3.4	1	Benchmarking platform doesn't sufficiently work	2	3	Early release of the software; embedding the technical team in the project team	Technical
Hub						
4.1	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The team will keep events concise. The team will make information easily accessible online.	Coordination
4.1	2	Community Managers do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	The team will have regular meetings with the entire Coordination Team, to keep up to date.	Staffing
4.1	3	An overload of ODISSEI communication, which lessens the interest of potential users.	1	2	The team will keep track of communication output in a Content Calendar.	Low Demand
4.2	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The education team will keep ODISSEI events concise. It will strive to match what it offers to researchers' needs and concentrate efforts in an intensive summer school.	Low Demand
4.2	2	Task team members do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	Regular meetings between the task team and Coordination Team. It will work closely with partners who do have specific knowledge.	Staffing
4.2	3	Demand for courses is too high	2	2	The task team will scale up events, and when needed, it will assist in coordinating 'train the trainer' events with ODISSEI partners.	High Demand
4.2	4	Demand for training is too low	2	3	The task team will work with the Community Management task (4.1) to increase ODISSEI's visibility. Integration in SICSS (task 4.5)	Low Demand

<i>Task</i>	<i>#</i>	<i>Risk</i>	<i>Prob¹</i>	<i>Imp²</i>	<i>Mitigating Action</i>	<i>Risk Area</i>
4.3	4	In the team, not being able to cover the wide range of required skills	1	3	(1) By spending 1 FTE on the wide expertise of the UU ITS team, wide range of skills available; (2) network of experts in UU focus area ADS (3) participating in SIGs of NLeSC.	Staffing
4.3	5	Not finding sufficient projects	2	3	Active acquisition, close collaboration with community management, close collaboration with operational management	Low Demand
4.3	6	Fewer applications to NLeSC grants than expected	2	2	After careful consideration, the new rounds of NLeSC grants were cancelled. The remaining budget was allocated to projects that meet strategic goals of ODISSEI.	Low Demand

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